

Photo-thermal models for predicting flowering in IR36 across locations. Screened data set of 43 trials from a global rice-weather study. 1987.

Model	Regression coefficients ^a				R ²	CV
	a	b	c	d		
<i>Seeding to flowering</i>						
1. 1/f = a + b*Tmean	-0.00165ns (0.00233)	0.00471** (0.00009)	-	-	0.39	13.0
2. 1/f = a + b*TU	0.02171** (0.000994)	-0.0000425** (3.93 E-07)	-	-	0.75	8.2
3. 1/f = a + b *TU+c*p+d*p ²	0.0733** (0.0236)	-0.0000385** (4.57 × 10 E-10)	0.0148** (0.00366)	-0.000579** (0.000141)	0.79	6.8
<i>Transplanting to flowering</i>						
1. 1/f = a + b*Tmean	-0.00334ns (0.00359)	+0.000695** (0.00138)	-	-	0.37	12.7
2. 1/f = a + b*TU	0.0302** (0.00117)	-8.64 E-06** (6.44 E-07)	-	-	0.81	7.0
3. 1/f = a + b*TU+c*p+d*p ²	-0.0707* (0.0307)	-8.15 E-06** (8.28 E-07)	+0.0156** (0.00476)	-0.000607** (0.00184)	0.78	6.3

^a*, ** = 0.05 and 0.01 significance levels, respectively, ns = estimated values not significant at the 5% level. 1/f = progress toward flowering, i.e., the reciprocal of the time from seeding to flowering (SF) or transplanting to flowering (TF). p = photoperiod. TU = accumulated thermal units. Tmean = mean temperature (°C) from seeding to flowering.

latitude groups. The optimum temperature for maximum development rate in IR36 was 26.8 °C.

A simple model using accumulated thermal units accurately estimated the rate of progress toward flowering (see table). Best fit models included a quadratic photoperiod term (p) that accounted for daylength effects. Models for genotypes maturing earlier (IR9729-67-3 and BG35-2) and later (Taichung Sen Yu 285) than IR36 were very similar in performance.

These data may be useful in developing simulation models of rice growth and development that rely on an accurate prediction of phenological events under a wide range of temperatures and daylengths. □

Grain quality and nutritional value

Optical determination of rice grain chalkiness (Clk)

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We used a digital grain translucency meter (DWY-1A model, manufactured by ZAAS) to measure grain translucency of 17 IR varieties grown in

Grain translucency and Clk rating in milled rice of 17 IR varieties, evaluated by digital translucency meter. Hangzhou, China, 1986.

Variety	Translucency (%)	Clk
IR22	90.7	1.4
IR24	81.0	2.8
IR28	84.0	2.6
IR30	70.0	6.5
IR34	88.0	3.3
IR36	86.3	3.2
IR38	80.7	5.2
IR43	79.7	3.9
IR44	84.3	3.6
IR45	86.7	5.0
IR46	82.3	1.0
IR52	78.7	1.4
IR54	89.0	1.5
IR56	85.0	1.0
IR60	85.7	1.0
IR62	90.7	1.0
IR64	77.3	4.1

early season 1986. Samples of whole milled rice were tested, with three replications.

Mean translucency and corresponding Clk scale are shown in the table. A significant negative correlation was

found between grain translucency and Clk (see figure). For rice breeding work or in grading for market value, this meter can be used instead of visual rating to measure the degree of Clk. Optical determination of Clk is not possible with waxy rice because the opaque endosperm also reduces grain translucency. □

Relationship between Clk scale and translucency measured in milled rice of 17 IR varieties, 1986.